

Phase-Averaged Analysis of Three-Dimensional Vorticity in the Wake of Two Yawed Side-By-Side Circular Cylinders

Authors : T. Zhou, S. F. Mohd Razali, Y. Zhou, H. Wang, L. Cheng

Abstract : The wake flow behind two yawed side-by-side circular cylinders is investigated using a three-dimensional vorticity probe. Four yaw angles (α), namely, 0° , 15° , 30° and 45° and two cylinder spacing ratios T^* of 1.7 and 3.0 were tested. For $T^* = 3.0$, there exist two vortex streets and the cylinders behave as independent and isolated ones. The maximum contour value of the coherent stream-wise vorticity is only about 10% of that of the spanwise vorticity. With the increase of α , increases whereas decreases. At $\alpha = 45^\circ$, is about 67% of. For $T^* = 1.7$, only a single peak is detected in the energy spectrum. The span-wise vorticity contours have an organized pattern only at $\alpha = 0^\circ$. The maximum coherent vorticity contours of and for $T^* = 1.7$ are about 30% and 7% of those for $T^* = 3.0$. The independence principle (IP) in terms of Strouhal numbers is applicable in both wakes when $\alpha < 40^\circ$.

Keywords : circular cylinder wake, vorticity, vortex shedding, side-by-side

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